

Virtual cohort generation for *in silico* trials of transcatheter aortic valve implantation

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In silico trials can increase the efficiency of development of transcatheter aortic valve implantation devices. They require large virtual cohorts of aortic stenosis (AS) patients, composed of four main components: a stenosed aortic valve geometry; a physiological model, simulating patient's hemodynamics; appropriate boundary conditions; and a distribution of calcifications across the geometry. This study aims to generate synthetic, virtual patients including these components, using a data set of 97 real AS patients. Aortic valve geometries from CT images are parameterized with 33 shape parameters, resulting from a statistical shape model. Left ventricular and aorta pressure signals, invasively measured with pressure wires, are parameterized with 10 parameters, by combining them with a lumped circulation model, through data assimilation. 3D calcification objects from CT images, are mapped to valve geometry elements. These 2D patterns are described by Gaussian random fields (GRFs), modelling the spatial distribution of calcium deposits. Each valve point is a random variable following a joint multivariate normal distribution, with a covariance function capturing spatial correlation between valve locations. A fluid-structure-interaction model is applied to the aortic valve geometries. Left ventricular and aorta pressure signals are prescribed at the inflow and outflow boundaries, respectively. Leaflets are modelled as a linear elastic material. Calcified leaflet elements get a high Young's modulus of 100 MPa, and that of the remaining part is determined by inverse modelling. Each real patient is described by 44 parameters (1 Young's modulus, 33 shape and 10 lumped parameters). Synthetic patients are generated by sampling points from a 44D distribution, fitted to the real data, and generating GRFs for the calcium distribution. These methods are integrated into a single virtual cohort generator, enabling the creation of any number of virtual patients. Being able to generate large, realistic data sets, without depending on patient data, is a significant step towards implementing *in silico* trials in the validation chain for cardiovascular implantable devices.

